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The Biblical Meaning of the Good Shepherd in John 10:1–11: A Scriptural Review and Faith-Theological Analysis

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Abstract.

The purpose of this paper is to demystify the biblical meaning of “Good Shepherd” as used by our Lord Jesus Christ in the book of John 10:1-11. This is important because the study will disabuse the misconceptions of the concept and unravel the qualities imbedded in the metaphor, *I am the Good Shepherd* as claimed by Jesus. Thus, this paper adopts a faith-theological methodology, employing scriptural review, critical exegesis, and an explanatory model. Faith theology is regarded as a theological inquiry that is built on Scripture and faith as an epistemological tool to uncover divine truths, and divine knowledge is revealed and received through faith, not empirical proof. This involves Scripture, as divine revelation, the ultimate source of truth, interpreted by faith rather than experimentation or observation. The researcher made a thorough scriptural and faith-theological analysis of John 10:11 in this paper. The findings of this study reveal that the contemporary leaders (religious and secular alike) should see their positions as simply that of service and sacrifice rather than one of exploitation and benefits. The paper concludes with some recommendations that will help to expand the frontiers of knowledge in biblical-theological studies and transform the church and the entire society.

Keywords: *good shepherd, shepherd, sheep, faith theology, scriptural review, Jesus*

Thesis Statement.

The researcher seeks to address the problem of the appropriate context of interpreting the Good Shepherd discourse. Addressing these problems will be one of the ways this paper hopes to bring about the original meaning of the text for the church and its implications for today’s readers.

1.0. Introduction.

The shepherd is a prominent, meaningful metaphor in the Bible. In fact, Adonai is referred to as a shepherd in Genesis 49:24¹ and Isaiah 40:11. In the latter, God is described as a tender shepherd who cares for His people, the flock. “He tends His flock like a shepherd: He gathers the lambs in His arms and carries them close to His heart; He gently leads those that have young” (Isaiah 40:11). Isaiah notes that the Messiah will come back as a shepherd comes to care for his sheep. In Psalm 23, the Psalmist tells us that the Lord is our shepherd and He protects His flock from evil. The chief care of the shepherd is to see that the sheep find plenty to eat and drink. The flocks are not fed in pens or folds, but must depend upon foraging for their sustenance (Psalms 23:2).

A prophetic passage in Micah speaks of Messiah as the Good Shepherd. Yet this shepherd is also Yahweh. He is called "the Breaker," [i.e., the One who breaks open the sheepfold to lead his to safety]. "I [God speaking] will surely gather all of you, O Jacob; I will surely bring together the remnant of Israel. I will bring them together like sheep in a pen, like a flock in its pasture; the place will throng with people ["in a great commotion"]. One who breaks open the way [Hebrew: *ha parats* will go up before them; they will break through the gate and go out. Their king will pass on before them, the LORD [Yahweh] at their head." (Micah 2:12-13).

Furthermore, sheep are more helpless and have to be led to their food (compare Numbers 27:16, Numbers 27:17); they do not possess the instinct of many other animals for finding their way home (compare Ezekiel 34:6-8). They are notoriously helpless, wayward, and even stupid animals. Sheep are among the most helpless of animals, and they're not very bright. It is a difficult and full-time job to care for them. Sheep are in need of leadership. Without it, they wander off and are injured or killed. Isaiah explains that we are “all, like sheep, have gone astray, each of us has turned to our own way” (Isaiah 53:6). This was just as true in his time, 700 years before the birth of Jesus, as it is now.

The metaphor of the “flock,” an everyday feature of Jewish life, pervades the Old Testament. God Himself was known as Israel’s Shepherd (e.g., Gen. 48:15; 49:24; Ps. 23:1; 28:9; 77:20; 78:52;

¹ Excepted otherwise stated, all scriptural citations are from the Kings James Version.

80:1; Isa. 40:11; Jer. 31:9; Ezek. 34:11–31), and His people are the “sheep of his pasture” (e.g., Ps. 74:1; 78:52; 79:13; 95:7; 100:3; Ezek. 34:31). Jesus saw Himself as embodying the characteristics and expectations attached to this salvation-historical biblical figure.

In the New Testament, Jesus’ identification of Himself as the Good Shepherd gives hope to the lost sheep. Sheep in this context are not only ‘dependent creatures; singularly unintelligent, prone to wandering and unable to find their way to a shepherd.’ Because of our helplessness and tendency to wander and get lost as sheep, we need a Good Shepherd. The notion of good shepherding in the epistles resonates with those who would lead in the church.

Jesus Christ, in His role as the Good Shepherd, fulfils multiple roles for His sheep. He is their guide, their protector, their healer, and their shepherd. His sheep, like all living beings, require spiritual sustenance, healing, care, love, and mercy. The first thing in His work as the Good Shepherd is that He has other sheep that are not of this fold (John 10:14-16). Here Jesus is lifting His eyes beyond the cross, beyond the resurrection, to the going forth of the gospel to all the nations of the earth. The result of that laying down of His life was that the gospel broke out beyond the boundaries of Israel and spread throughout the earth. Here we are, at the far corners of the world, meeting as a great crowd of believers in Jesus because He laid down His life for the sheep. He brought us together so that there is one flock -- not one fold, notice, but one flock - and one shepherd, no more than one; one church, one Lord, as Paul says in Ephesians 4.

1.1. Aim of the Research Work.

The basic theological intent of this research work is to discover the biblical meaning of the Good Shepherd (John 10:1-11). This biblical meaning is intended to uncover and present a profound message about the sacrificial love and role of Jesus as the caring and faithful Good Shepherd of His followers. With the aid of the original biblical meaning which shall be used, the researcher hope to arrive at conclusions that are scholarly plausible and inter-subjectively verifiable and acceptable. A review of this work will further enrich the present exegetical study on John 10:1-11.

1.2. Research Questions.

The following research questions will guide the study:

- a. What is the biblical meaning of “Good Shepherd” as it is used in John 10 by our Lord Jesus Christ?
- b. Why God's flock is compared to sheep?
- c. Why Jesus choose to be identified with the picture of the Good Shepherd?

1.3. Research Problem.

One should note that in the New Testament all of the shepherding imagery follows the narrative of Jesus’ healing of the Man Born Blind. While worthy of further development, for our purposes here, let us simply say that John’s theological intent is to show the religious leaders as blind shepherds in their failure, same as it is today also, to recognize the healing light that is in Jesus the Messiah. This presents a profound message about the sacrificial love of Jesus and His role as the caring and faithful shepherd of His followers. These qualities of love and care that present Jesus as a Good Shepherd are lacking in some of the contemporary religious leaders. This study is, therefore, set to fill these gaps by unravelling the biblical meaning of the phrase, *The Good Shepherd*.

1.4. Research Methodology.

The research methodology adopted in this paper is faith-theology employing scriptural review and exegetical method to unravel the meaning of *The Good Shepherd* in John 10:1-11. Faith-theological approach is adopted because, according to Dele Alaba Ilesanmi (2025), it is the legitimate mode of both the abstracted and concreted realities of divine truth, grounded in non-empirical, faith-based knowledge, in order to understand God's nature, will, and relationship with the universe.² Ilesanmi further avers that faith theology is regarded as a theological inquiry that is built on Scripture and faith as an epistemological tool to discover divine truths, asserting that divine knowledge is revealed and received through faith, not empirical proof. Therefore, Scripture, as divine revelation, becomes the ultimate source of truth, interpreted by faith rather than

² Ilesanmi, Dele A. “Faith Theology as a Non-Empirical Approach to Understanding Divine Truth: A Study of Abstracted and Concreted Realities” in *International Journal of Biblical Studies*, 2025, vol. 1(1).

experimentation or observation (Romans 10:17; 2 Timothy 3:16-17), without which our theology is considered *atheology*³

2.0. Scriptural Review and Exegesis.

In a work titled, *The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review*, Ilesanmi (2025)⁴ asserts that “Scriptural review refers to the process of studying, analysing, and applying scripture to life, ministry, or research,” stressing that it involves examining biblical texts, understanding their context, drawing conclusions, and applications. Ilesanmi emphasises further that “the purpose of scriptural review is to develop biblical insights, principles, theories, and concepts to inform decision-making, problem-solving, identification of Theowordiness gaps or word gaps in existing research, develop research questions, and inform research design from a biblical frame of reference.” Indeed, Scriptural review brings a deeper understanding and correct interpretation of God’s word.⁵ Drawing from this insight, the meaning of “Good Shepherd” cannot be unravelled without the Bible.

John 10 begins with the distinctive expression of the Johannine Jesus: ‘Truly, truly I say to you...’ (Ἀμὴν ἀμὴν λέγω ὑμῖν...). Since the Greek text here records the Aramaic or Hebrew term ‘Amen’, then we should really do so in English translations, as we do for other Aramaic terms like ‘Marana tha’, ‘Alleluia’ (in Revelation), and ‘Amen’ when it occurs in its usual place at the end of a prayer or praise to God. ‘Amen’ concludes numerous prayers in the OT, but only Jesus uses it to introduce His solemn statements. The single use (‘Amen I say to you...’) occurs throughout Matthew and Mark, suggesting that this is a record of Jesus’ ipsissima verba, though Luke mostly omits the phrase in order to make his gospel more accessible to a non-Jewish readership (for example, compare Matt 8.10 with Luke 7.9). The Fourth gospel’s unique doubling of ‘Amen’, which comes 25 times, is usually repeated three or four times within a narrative unit, and almost always occurs in the middle of a section of discourse - and this is no exception.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ilesanmi, Dele A. “The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review” in *International Journal of Biblical Studies*, 2025, vol. 1(1).

⁵ Ibid.

Part-way through Jesus' discourse about the sheep/shepherd/sheepfold, the gospel narrator interjects to explain that this is a 'figure of speech', a **paroimia**. The term **paroimia** translates the Hebrew term "mashal" in the Greek OT (the Septuagint, LXX). The first part of the **paroimia** is simply descriptive of the practices of shepherd in Jesus' day. There is often discussion here as to whether shepherds were social outcasts as the bottom rung of the ladder of respectability. However, all the negative references to shepherds either come from Greek sources or from one part of the Babylonian Talmud, which might have been influenced polemically against the gospel traditions in which shepherds are positive models. Within this narrative, and elsewhere in the NT, shepherds are depicted entirely positively - which is not surprising given the roots of the image in the OT as referring to God and to those who are faithful leaders under God of His people, especially in Ezekiel 34 and Psalms 23. First-century shepherds would indeed be able to name their sheep, who would respond to either a tune played on a flute by their shepherd, or the shepherd calling them by name.

In the second part of the **paroimia**, Jesus makes His identification with the shepherd and the door explicit, and this section includes, close together, two of the seven 'I am...' sayings of the Fourth Gospel. "I am the good shepherd..." (John 10:11) is a declarative statement. Jesus in this passage declares Himself to be the Good Shepherd. The emphasis here is not just on being a shepherd but the adjective "good" is added to denote the kind of shepherd He is. This shepherd-sheep relationship is what the writer of this passage portrays as the relationship between Jesus and His people. So Jesus' claims here contribute to the high Christology of this gospel; what God was to Israel, Jesus now is to those who follow Him. Jesus' willingness, as the Good Shepherd, to lay down His life in John 10:11 clearly anticipates the crucifixion. One observes that the verb "laying (τιθησιν) down" as used in this text shows the extent of His sacrifice. The imagery of the shepherd and sheep used here is very significant.

3.0. Theo-Theoretical and Conceptual Framework.

Here, there shall be an analysis of the underlying concept and ideas that are seen in this text, John 10:11. A closer attention shall be given to them here with special emphasis on the background against which they were used. The first is the word **shepherd**. A shepherd is one who pastures or tends a flock of sheep. Many important figures in the history of the Hebrews were shepherds including Abraham, Isaac and Jacob. The work of the shepherd involves the routine of leading the

sheep to food and water, and then returning them to the safety of the fold. Due to the vulnerability of the sheep, the shepherd has to be on the watch out for the strays and count the sheep as they enter their enclosure for the night (Leviticus 27:32, Jeremiah 33:13). If any was missing, it is the duty of the shepherd to look for and rescue the lost (Ezekiel 34:11-12). Special attention was given to the sick and to the new born lambs. In addition, the shepherds also made use of staff to control the movement of the flock and the rod to ward off enemies. Some passages in the scripture like Job 30:1 mention the use of dogs in order to help manage the movement of the sheep. Other instances of shepherd in the New Testament include Matthew 18:12-14, Luke 2:8-10.

The next is the word **Life**. Life is the principle or force considered to underlie the distinctive quality of animate beings. It is used in the Bible to describe the animating force in both animals and humans (Genesis 1:20). This physical bodily existence is subject to suffering, illness, toil, death, temptations and sin (Psalms 89:47; 103:14). Life as used in the Bible however has a much wider application than only to physical, bodily existence. The Old Testament refers mainly to “one’s life span on earth (Deuteronomy 4:9) and is often contrasted with death.” Death is often understood as the end of life. No soul or part of a person lives on after death. In the New Testament, “life generally refers to life after death, eternal life even though the New Testament often uses the Old Testament understanding of the term.” In the text of John 10:11, the Good Shepherd who is Jesus lays down His earthly life as man for the sake of the flock.

The next word to be examined is the **sheep**. The sheep is seen as a ruminant mammal related to the goat. Sheep are mentioned in the Bible more than five hundred times. In the Old Testament, the sheep is used in the literal sense (Deut 32:14, Num 32:24) while in the New Testament, they are mainly used as metaphors (Matt 10:6, Heb 13:20). The Bible provides various references to the skill of the shepherd who knows each of the animals by name and whose voice is recognized by the sheep (John 10:3-4, Ezekiel 34:15-16). The constant search for greener pasture remains the regular task of those who tend the sheep (1 Chronicles 4:39-40).

4.0. The Biblical Meaning of Good Shepherd

4.1. Shepherd and Sheep in Asia Minor.

“Sheep,” here, is understood as a metaphoric term for human beings as frail and dependent creatures who are not able to conduct their lives on their own. It is in this light that the shepherd is

understood as the leader of the people. The characteristics that were applied to Apollo and Hermes - two Greek deities which were regarded as shepherds in Asia Minor - are similar to the characteristics of the shepherd in John 10. The two prominent features between Hermes and Jesus as metaphorical shepherds are their function as gatekeepers and also their task of leading their sheep to pasture or the realms of the afterlife. It is further identified that Apollo shares certain characteristic features with Jesus: he is described as the attendant of the sheep, the pastoral and the door keeper who averts evil from entering the gates of the city. These go to show the possibility of the influence of Greek thinking and philosophy on John.

4.2. Shepherd and Sheep in the Ancient Near East.

The imagery of the "shepherd" and "flock" are used in the Ancient Near East more frequently than in Greek literature. The shepherd's crook is usually an emblem of royal authority. The Egyptian pyramid texts apply the shepherd image to the ruler of the world who is to come. Osiris or the dead Pharaoh is here portrayed as the one who protects his subjects even in the underworld. During the time of the middle kingdom, the reigning king is also portrayed as a shepherd.

Apart from its use of the shepherd metaphor for Joshua (Numbers 21:17) and Moses (Deuteronomy 31:1), the Old Testament does not usually use the shepherd imagery for the Israelite kings. It is usually reserved for God to portray His care and the nature of His rule of the people of Israel (Ps 23:1-4, 74:1, Ezekiel 34 and many other such passages). In the New Testament, the application of the shepherd metaphor to God is continued in the Jesus parables (Luke 15:4-7; Matthew 18:12-14). Jesus is referred to as the one who cares for the lost and the one who oversees the flock. In Revelation 7:17, He is described as both the victorious shepherd and the lamb who leads those who survive the tribulations to the spring of living waters.

4.3 Origins of Shepherd Metaphor.

The Greek word "kalos," translated "good," describes that which is noble, wholesome, good, and beautiful in contrast to that which is wicked, mean, foul, and unlovely. It signifies not only that which is good inwardly but also that which is attractive outwardly. It is an innate goodness. The Greek text in John 10:11 and John 10:14 uses the definite article "the" before "good shepherd." The definite article claims this ["I am the good shepherd"] as a description applicable to Jesus alone. Therefore, in using the phrase "the good shepherd," Jesus is referencing His inherent

goodness, His righteousness, and His beauty. As shepherd of the sheep, He is the one who protects, guides, and nurtures His flock.

To better understand the purpose of a shepherd during the times of Jesus, it is helpful to realize that sheep are utterly defenseless and totally dependent upon the shepherd. Sheep are always subject to danger and must always be under the watchful eye of the shepherd as they graze because robbers may steal them, and wolves may attack the flock. Shepherds were frequently subjected to grave danger, sometimes even giving their lives to protect their sheep. In proclaiming that He is the Good Shepherd, Jesus speaks of “laying down” His life “for” His sheep (John 10:15, 17-18). The word “for” in John 10:11 refers to the substitutionary death of Christ. Christ died “for” us or “instead” of us. He died in our place so we may live. Overall, John 10:11 encapsulates the core teachings of Christianity, emphasizing the selfless and redemptive nature of Jesus's love. It serves as a powerful reminder of the depth of God's love and the extent to which Jesus is willing to go to ensure the well-being and salvation of His people.

5.0. Discussions.

The “good shepherd” remains the dominant theme in this passage. As shown earlier, Jesus appropriates this imagery to Himself as shown in John’s Gospel. The Good Shepherd is so called because of His relationship with the Father, and this relationship involves a specific mission of subjecting Himself to death for the sake of His sheep. On another dimension, the Good Shepherd informs the audience about the presence of the other sheep which are from another fold that must be brought into the same fold as those which are presumably in His audience. In the Jewish setting, the idea of one shepherd ruling Israel was already common place in Jewish thinking. Jesus extends the traditional idea here by referring to other sheep that will be brought over into the same fold. As a Good Shepherd who seeks the unity of the flock, His aim will be to bring the other sheep together so that there will be one flock and one shepherd.

The construction “I am” followed by the predicate in the mouth of Jesus and in reference to Himself is exclusive to John in the New Testament. The unifying criterion of the shepherd image is the pastoral love or charity of the shepherd. He is presented as the shepherd for others. All the actions He does have a relation to the sheep that is entrusted to Him. His life is projected towards the safety, well being and the growth of the sheep notwithstanding the consequences this might

have on Him. All these spring from His love; a love He receives from the Father and which He transmits to all those who were given to Him. Jesus the Good Shepherd comes so as to liberate the sheep from the hands of the wicked shepherds and to lead them to freedom and to good pastures. In Jesus, “the new spiritual exodus finds its consummation so that he who believes in Him may not remain in darkness.” His love for those whom the Father gave Him does not stop at the boundaries of His fold but goes beyond it in order to bring together other sheep. Thus, He forms one flock under one shepherd.

The love of Jesus for the sheep is also manifested in a particular way in His personal, intimate knowledge of the sheep. He knows each one by name and calls each one to follow Him. The sheep hear His voice; they recognize it and follow Him. There is then a communion that exists between Jesus and the sheep, a communion that is the fruit of the reciprocal communion between the Father and the Son. This communion urges the Good Shepherd to give Himself completely for the sheep by laying down His life.

6.0. Findings

1. The research identifies a high concentration of metaphorical and figurative language in John 10.
2. The purpose of the Good Shepherd discourse is to present the image of Jesus as the Good Shepherd as against the false shepherds.
3. John uses the shepherd imagery to set forth for his audience the significance of Jesus, since it was well known to the Jews and Gentiles as a picture of leadership and salvation for humanity.
4. The shepherd discourse also becomes a model for contemporary leaders (religious and secular alike) to see their positions as simply that of service and sacrifice rather than one of exploitation and benefits.

7.0. Impacts

The Old Testament texts as well as John 10 function in a context of the shepherdlessness of the covenant community of God. As part of the pastoral Christology of John, John 10:1-11 presents us with the ultimate figure of the Good Shepherd who answers to the need of the shepherdless covenant community. The researcher think, therefore, that the shepherd discourse has a

contemporary significance and impact where the Church of God lacks credible shepherds and where the believing community is scattered. These include the experience of non-unity among believers; the possibility that churches, church organizations or ministers do not serve but rather turn themselves into agents of exploitation and division; the experience of the lack of shepherds by believers whose material, social and spiritual needs are ignored.

8.0. Recommendations

1. Like sheep, people are prone to wander, always searching for greener grass, and too often oblivious to danger. As shepherds, church leaders are to be watchful, keeping their flock safe from their own tendency to wander. This protects them from dangerous terrain and waiting predators.
2. The primary responsibility of the clergy is to their local flock. They need to follow the paradigm of Jesus who laid down His life for the people; they should always show concern for the local assembly which they are placed in charge of. It is very much recommended that they have close, impactful relationship with the flock and not some long-distance relationship.
3. Clerics who hold or occupy secular leadership positions should learn from Jesus the Good Shepherd to be more dedicated to their duties and shun corruption, discrimination, and sectionalism of all forms that breed discord.
4. In all, contemporary secular leaders should develop the mentality of seeing their positions as privileged moments to serve and not to be served. Having such an outlook will certainly lead to the development of the society.

9.0. Conclusion

By employing faith-theological examination, the study is able to address the concrete human pastoral situations, explain and unravel the biblical meaning of Good shepherd, the concept of sheep, and why the contemporary religious leaders and other leaders, including the secular sphere, should imbibe the qualities of love and caring of our Lord Jesus Christ. Thus, Jesus in His ministry on earth was in touch with human feelings and situations; He is the Shepherd with the smell of the sheep. His extravagant love for the sheep can be described as a love-unto-death. This, among others, the study has contributed to expand the frontiers of knowledge in Scripture-govern theological studies.

Bibliography.

- Bruce Metzger. *A Textual Commentary on The Greek New Testament*, New York: United Bible Societies, 1971.
- C. K. Barrett. *The Gospel According to St John. An Introduction With Commentary and Notes on The Greek Text*. SPCK, London, 1967.
- Colin Brown. *The New International Dictionary of the New Testament*. Regency Reference Library (vol. 2), 1971.
- Colin G. Kruse, John. An Introduction and Commentary in Tyndale New Testament Commentaries, InterVarsity Press, Downers Grove, IL, vol. 4, 2003.
- Gail R. O'Day. John in the New Interpreter's Bible, Abingdon Press, Nashville, TN, vol. 9 ed., 1996.
- Gerhard Kittel, et.al. *Theological Dictionary of the New Testament*, Grand Rapids, Michigan, 1995.
- Harper Collins Bible Dictionary. "Shepherd." Theological Publications, Bangalore, 2009.
- Holman Illustrated Bible Dictionary. "Shepherd," Holman Bible Publishers, Tennessee, 1998.
- Ilesanmi, Dele A. "Faith Theology as a Non-Empirical Approach to Understanding Divine Truth: A Study of Abstracted and Concreted Realities" in *International Journal of Biblical Studies*, 2025, vol. 1(1).
- Ilesanmi, Dele A. "The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review" in *International Journal of Biblical Studies*, 2025, vol. 1(1).
- Raymond E. Brown (1966), *The Gospel According to John*, Doubleday Press, New York, NY, 1996.
- Rudolf Bultmann. *The Gospel of John: A Commentary*, Westminster, Philadelphia, 1971.
- Thomas Brodie. *The Gospel According to John*, Oxford University Press, New York, 1973.

